

Alternative Treatments for Minor GI Ailments

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1. Abstract

About 80% of the population worldwide use a variety of traditional medicine, including herbal medicines, for the diagnosis, prevention and treatment of illnesses, and for the improvement of general well-being. Total consumer spending on herbal dietary supplements in the United States reached an estimated \$8.085 billion in 2017. In addition, the 8.5% increase in total sales from 2016 is the strongest growth for these products in more than 15 years. The main reason to use herbal products in these countries is the assumption of a better tolerability compared to synthetic drugs. Whereas in developing countries herbal medicines are mostly the only available and affordable treatment option. Surveys from industrialized countries reveal as main health areas in which herbal products are used upper airway diseases including cough and common cold; other leading causes are gastrointestinal, nervous and urinary complaints up to painful conditions such as rheumatic diseases, joint pain and stiffness. Gastrointestinal disorders are the most widespread problems in health care. Many factors may upset the GI tract and its motility (or ability to keep moving), including: eating a diet low in fiber; lack of motion or sedentary lifestyle; frequent traveling or changes in daily routine; having excessive dairy products; anxiety and depression; resisting the urge to have a bowel movement habitually or due to pain of hemorrhoids; misuse of laxatives (stool softeners) that, over time, weaken the bowel muscles; calcium or aluminum antacids, antidepressants, iron pills, narcotics; pregnancy. About 30% to 40% of adults claim to have frequent indigestion, and over 50 million visits are made annually to ambulatory care facilities for symptoms related to the digestive system. Over 10 million endoscopies and surgical procedures involving the GI tract are performed each year. Community-based studies from around the world demonstrate that 10% to 46% of all children meet the criteria for RAP. Gastrointestinal disorders such as chronic or acute diarrhea, malabsorption, abdominal pain, and inflammatory bowel diseases can indicate immune deficiency, present in 5% to 50% of patients with primary immunodeficiencies. The gastrointestinal tract is the largest lymphoid organ in the body, so it is not surprising that intestinal diseases are common among immunodeficient patients. Gastroenterologists therefore must be able to diagnose and treat patients with primary immunodeficiency. Further, pathogens do influence the gut function. On the other hand, dietary habits and specific food types can play a significant role in the onset, treatment, and prevention of many GI disorders. Many of these can be prevented or minimized by maintaining a healthy lifestyle, and practicing good bowel habits.

Keywords: Herbs; Bowel; Gastric Mucosa; Probiotics; Economic Burden; HRQoL

Purpose of The Study: Review of proper utilization foods, herbs and other alternative treatment options to prevent minor GI disorders.

Methodology: Comprehensive literature search followed by consulting healthcare professionals about GI disorders. Hospital, clinic and company personnel, newspaper journalists, NGO workers and a few folk healers, alternative medicine specialists given their valuable suggestions. A few western magazine and newspapers also observed to get the necessary concern. The present study was started from the beginning of 2018. PubMed, ALTAVISTA, Embase, Scopus, Web of Science, and the Cochrane Central Register of was thoroughly searched. The keywords were used to search for different publishers' journals like Elsevier, Springer, Willey Online Library, Wolters Kluwer were extensively followed. Projections were based on public life pattern, their food habits, contamination sources, different uses of available herbs and daily consumed foods, their medicinal values in minor GI ailments.

Findings: Conventional treatments unable to prove themselves in GI disorders more often. Complimentary drugs, probiotics along with food and lifestyle adjustment according to suggested guideline ensures patient satisfaction, improves HRQoL, reduce exacerbation. Further research necessary to both system of medicine to be more trustworthy and to ensure more fruitful outcome in this arena.

Limitation of the study: Lack of recent statistical research data found in this arena of study, however, data obtained from valid sources are added to this article.

Practical Implication: Along with pharmacists, pharmacy students, physicians, nurses and other health workers, policy makers, conscious general people have to assimilate many subject matters from this article.

Article Highlights:

1. About 80% of the population worldwide use a variety of traditional medicine.
2. Sales of HDS in US passed \$8 billion in 2017, with 8.5% increase in total sales from 2016.
3. In community settings, almost 50% of patients with FGIDs used CAM therapies
4. GERD affects up to 40% of the population, 40%-50% of patients with GERD have abnormal peristalsis.
5. 20–30% continue to experience reflux symptoms despite PPI treatment
6. Dyspepsia affects 20% of the global population, 30–70% of the patients with functional dyspepsia experience delayed gastric emptying.
7. Dyspepsia prevalence was 30.4% in India, 24% in Spain and 45% in Nigeria.
8. The prevalence of functional dyspepsia is 12-15% in patients with IBS.
9. 30% of the general population experiences constipation during life time but incidence sometimes rises up to 80% in critically ill patients.
10. The economic burden of IBS in the U.S. is estimated at \$28 billion annually, 32% of IBS-C patients suffer depression as their condition almost every day in the previous month.
11. Sexual dysfunction is positively associated with perceived GI symptom severity and HRQoL

Figure 1. Graphical Abstract

2. Introduction

The digestive system is dedicated to breaking down food and allowing its nutrients to be absorbed into the bloodstream, from where they are then carried to every part of the body. Spices and herbal remedies have been used since ancient times to treat a variety of disorders. It has been experimentally demonstrated that spices, herbs, and their extracts possess antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antirheumatic, lipid-lowering, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, antimutagenic and anticancer activities, besides their gastroprotective and anti-ulcer activities. Nowadays, several experimental studies and, to a lesser extent, clinical trials have also emphasized the role of herbs in the treatment of a variety of disorders. Several herbs and herbal extracts have been shown to possess antibacterial properties. For instance, onion, garlic, ginger, pepper and mustard have demonstrated antimicrobial activity against several types of bacteria. Tayel and El-Tras have recently reported a potent antibacterial activity of cinnamon and clove against several bacterial strains. Some spices possess antifungal activity. Beside their antifungal activity, herbs have also shown vermifugal, nematocidal and molluscicidal potential. In addition, gingerol, the active ingredient of ginger, and eugenol have shown anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic activity. More recent studies have also demonstrated anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic properties of herbs. Furthermore, gingerol and curcumin have also shown lipid-lowering potential in experimental animals as well as in clinical trials. The mechanism of epigastric pain and dyspepsia induced by red and black pepper is not well-defined. However, it is believed to be a consequence of inhibition of gastric surface hydrophobicity, enhancement of surface wettability and activation of intramucosal pain receptors. Some spices may stimulate acid secretion and have deleterious effects on the gastric mucosal lining. Intra-gastric perfusion of albino rats with aqueous extracts of red pepper, fennel, omum/ajwain, cardamom, black pepper, cumin and coriander have stimulated a cholinergic response, and/or via other mechanism(s) have induced acid secretion with a respectively.

3. GERD

The AGC guidelines define GERD as “symptoms or complications resulting from the reflux of gastric contents into the esophagus or beyond, into the oral cavity (including larynx) or lung. GERD is one of the most common diseases in society, affecting up to 40% of the population [22]. A systematic review demonstrated that the prevalence of GERD ranged from 18.1% to 27.8% in North America, 8.8% to 25.9% in Europe, 2.5% to 7.8% in East Asia, 8.7% to 33.1% in the Middle East, 11.6% in Australia, and 23.0% in South America [1]. The cardinal symptoms of GERD are heartburn and regurgitation. However, GERD may present with a variety of other symptoms, including water brash, chest pain or discomfort, dysphagia, belching, epigastric pain, nausea, and bloating. In addition, patients may experience extraesophageal symptoms like cough, hoarseness, throat clearing, throat pain or burning, wheezing, and sleep disturbances [2]. Approximately 50% of the patients presenting with heartburn have erosive esophagitis on upper endoscopy, up to 70% of these patients have normal endoscopy findings. Furthermore, 40% of those with normal endoscopy findings and normal pH test results have reflux hypersensitivity (a positive correlation between symptoms and reflux events), and 60% have functional heartburn [8]. Impaired aspects of quality of life are disturbed sleep, reduced vitality, generalized body pain, unsatisfactory sex life, and anxiety. Nocturnal symptoms caused by reflux appear to have a particularly marked influence on quality of life and the burden of illness imposed by GERD also has an impact on work productivity [23]. Studies have demonstrated that symptom frequency, severity, or combination of both are not predictive of any specific phenotypic presentation of GERD [3]. However, elderly patients with GERD appear to experience a more severe mucosal disease that is associated with overall milder and more atypical symptoms [4]. 40%-50% of patients with GERD have abnormal peristalsis. This dysmotility is particularly severe in about 20% of patients because of very low amplitude of peristalsis and/or abnormal propagation of the peristaltic waves (ineffective esophageal motility) [17]. Other symptoms of GERD include: sore throat; sour taste in the back of the mouth; asthma symptoms (prevalence of GERD found in 30% to 65% patients with asthma), dry cough; trouble swallowing [18,19]. Psychological comorbidity (anxiety, hypervigilance, depression, and somatization) does play an important role in patients with refractory heartburn [7]. GERD has emerged as a comorbidity of asthma and COPD. The prevalence of GERD in asthma patients has ranged from 25% to 80%, 38% of asthma patients had GERD in another study [1], [44]. The prevalence of GERD in COPD ranges from 17% to 78%. Although GERD is usually confined to the lower esophagus in some individuals, it may be associated with pulmonary micro-aspiration of gastric contents [45]. The overall prevalence of IBS symptoms in the GERD population ranges from 10-74% [64].

3.1. Lifestyle Modification for Gastroesophageal Reflux

Mediterranean (frequent consumption of composite/traditional dishes, fresh fruit and vegetables, olive oil, and fish) to a beneficial effect in the occurrence of GERD [24]. Patients with reflux often benefit from a diet that avoids specific food triggers. In particular, fatty foods, spicy foods, acidic foods, chocolate, and caffeine worsen reflux symptoms. Prior to completely eliminating wheat, a celiac screen should be performed with a tissue transglutaminase IgA antibody, and a total IgA level [21]. Even modest weight gain can exacerbate GERD symptoms and women who reduced their BMI by 3.5 units or more reported a 40% reduction in the frequency of GERD symptoms compared with controls [5]. Cessation of tobacco, alcohol, chocolate, caffeine or coffee, citrus, mint or spicy food may improve in clinical or physiological parameters of GERD [6]. Chewing gum stimulates the production of saliva, it helps dilute and clear the acid from unwanted areas [26].

Exhibit 1. Non-Drug Treatment Options of GERD [10], [20], [30]	
1.	Elevation of the bed head (15 cm)
2.	Moderation in the ingestion of the following foods (based on symptom correlation): fatty foods, citrus, coffee, alcoholic and/or carbonated beverages, mint, peppermint, tomato, chocolate
3.	Refraining from wearing tight-fitting clothes: Clothes that are tight around the waist can put extra pressure on your stomach. This added pressure can then affect the LES, increasing reflux.
4.	Avoidance of lying down in the 2 h following meals. Lying down too soon after meals can induce heartburn.
5.	Eliminate distractions at mealtime. Avoid reading, checking phone, or watching television while eating. Chew each bite thoroughly. Eat smaller meals rather than big meals. Overeating puts more pressure on lower esophageal sphincter.
6.	Quitting of smoking
7.	Reduction of body weight, if overweight

3.2. GERD Expenditure

GERD is a common, chronic, relapsing symptom. Often people self-diagnose and self-treat it even though health-related quality of life is significantly impaired. In the lack of a valid alternative approach, current treatments focus on suppression of gastric acid secretion by the use of PPIs, but people with GERD have a significantly lower response rate to therapy [9], approximately 20–30% continue to experience reflux symptoms despite PPI treatment [11]. 30–40% of patients receiving medical therapy with PPIs experience troublesome breakthrough symptoms, and recent evidence suggests that this therapy is related to increased risk of complications [12]. In the US alone, overall spending on all GI diseases is estimated to be \$142 billion (in 2009 US dollars) per year in direct and indirect costs. GERD accounts for approximately \$15–20 billion of these direct and indirect costs. It has been estimated that prescribed medications for GERD, primarily PPIs, account for over 50% of prescriptions for all digestive diseases, resulting in around \$10 billion in annual direct health care costs [25,26]. Extraesophageal manifestations of reflux, including LPR, asthma, and chronic cough, have been estimated to cost \$5438 per patient in direct medical expenses in the first year after presentation and \$13,700 for 5 years [28].

3.3. Herbs for GERD Management

Some research has also shown improved symptoms in people with GERD who take peppermint oil. Historically, ginger has been used to treat other gastrointestinal ailments, including heartburn. This may reduce overall swelling and irritation in the esophagus. Caraway, garden angelica, German chamomile flower, greater celandine, licorice root, lemon balm, milk thistle and turmeric have little clinical evidence to support their effectiveness [29]. Fermented foods, like kimchi (alkaline), can be incredibly helpful for digestive system. Consuming a spoonful of mustard during the onset of acid reflux symptoms of heartburn by balancing pH levels. Many patients have seen significant benefits from snacking tasty nuts (especially almond), to be consumed raw, organic and salt-free. Both bananas and apples contain natural antacids that can help relieve or prevent an onset of acid reflux [26]. Marshmallow (*Althea officinalis* L.) contains a mucilage quality (may interfere with the absorption of other medications) which helps to coat the esophagus and stomach lining, creating a protective barrier against stomach acid. It's an effective stimulator of cell physiology of epithelial cells which can prove the traditional use of Marshmallow preparations for treatment of irritated mucous membranes within tissue regeneration [31,32]. Chewing DGL (deglycyrrhizinated licorice) also helps boost enzyme production, allowing for easier and quicker digestion as well as better absorption of nutrients [32]. Use of low doses of pure glycyrrhetic acid and bilberry anthocyanosides, together with alginic acid as add-on therapy, substantially improves symptoms in patients with nonerosive reflux disease without increasing side effects or worsening tolerability or compliance [33]. To add to all that nutrition, papaya is an excellent treatment for acid reflux. It contains a proteolytic enzyme that breaks down proteins in the digestive system into amino acids. The active ingredient, papain, is helpful to the digestion of fats and carbs. It aids in digestion and allows body to make acid. The potassium in papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) also introduces healthy bacteria into intestines. This can prevent stomach from working as hard and helps to stop indigestion and reflux. Papaya is used as a natural remedy in abnormal digestion in tropical and industrialized countries [34-36]. The fenugreek fiber effects were generally similar to the results produced by an OTC antacid medication (ranitidine at 75 mg, twice a day). 2 weeks intake of a fenugreek fiber product, taken 30 min before two meals/day, diminished heartburn severity [37]. The cytoprotective effect of the seeds seemed to be not only due to the anti-secretory action but also to the effects on mucosal glycoproteins. The fenugreek seeds also prevented the rise in lipid peroxidation induced by ethanol presumably by enhancing antioxidant potential of the gastric mucosa thereby lowering mucosal injury. Histological studies revealed that the soluble gel fraction derived from the seeds was more effective than omeprazole in preventing lesion formation [38]. An involvement of *Opuntia ficus-indica* mucilages (mainly cultivated in the Mediterranean region and in Central America) has been hypothesized, mainly formed by arabinogalactan and galacturonic acid, forming a defense layer in these gastroprotective effects. The mucilage is strongly viscous which because of the negative charges causes strong intermolecular repulsion, resulting in expansion of the molecules. It is believed that this changing in molecular shape could be responsible for the protection of the gastric mucosa [13-15]. Olive leaf extract possesses antioxidant properties, which can positively influence gastroprotection. The main iridoide monoterpene oleuropein contained in olive leaf was usually thought to be responsible for pharmacological effects but it was recently observed that olive leaf is as a stable source of bioactive flavonoids. In fact, the contribution of flavonoids to the overall radical scavenging activity of olive leaf extracts has been investigated and luteolin 7-O-glucoside was found to be one of the dominant scavengers (8–25%) [16]. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) and its compounds (especially Curcumin) should be considered as a promising alternative for patients who suffer from digestive disorders because it is safe, inexpensive, and ubiquitously available. Curcumin has been defined as the most active component in *C. longa* and has considerable gastroprotective and antiulcerogenic effect. Improvement in clinical scores of GERD and GERD Activity Index is proven with turmeric [39,40]. German chamomile (*Matricaria recutita*) (contains flavonoids, in particular apigenin gastric shown protective effect in clinical trial) and bismuth have known

gastric protective properties, and *Atropa belladonna* contains anticholinergic agents that have bronchodilatory effect. Complementary treatments containing these ingredients could be used to treat patient with asthma patients having GERD, and if effective, could be an additional treatment tool that could also reduce the use of long-term inhaled corticosteroids and proton pump inhibitor treatment and thus their side effects [41]. Although a number of toxic effects have been attributed to bismuth compounds in humans: nephropathy, encephalopathy, osteoarthropathy, gingivitis, stomatitis and colitis. Whether hepatitis is a side effect, however, is open to dispute [42]. Aloe Vera was safe and well tolerated and reduced the frequencies of all the assessed GERD symptoms, but nephrotoxicity and hepatotoxicity (also human carcinogen, Group 2B) is keeping its use in a controversial position [46-49].

4. Dyspepsia

Dyspepsia is common, affecting approximately 20% of the global population, and is frequently encountered in primary care. Functional dyspepsia (FD) is one of the most prevalent gastrointestinal disorders, and is defined as a chronic disease with persistent upper gastrointestinal symptoms without any explanatory organic or metabolic causes [50]. Dyspepsia is a very common GI complaint, with up to one in five individuals affected worldwide. Of those with dyspepsia, around 40% will seek the advice of their primary care physician. Almost 15% of patients with dyspepsia are referred to secondary care for further investigation and management [58]. When broadly defined, dyspepsia occurs in 40%, leads to GP consultation in 5% and referral for endoscopy in 1% of the population annually. In patients with signs or symptoms severe enough to merit endoscopy, 40% have functional or non-ulcer dyspepsia, 40% have GERD and 13% have some form of ulcer [62]. Heartburn and acid regurgitation are no longer considered to be symptoms of dyspepsia, but of GER. Both the underlying causes and progress of functional dyspepsia are still unknown. That is largely true of GERD as well [65]. One-third of patients who visit general physician practices are patients with dyspepsia syndrome; and half of patients who visit gastroenterologists are also patients with dyspepsia syndrome [66]. The prevalence of functional dyspepsia was UK (21%), US (26%), Jordan (60%), western Iran (18%), China (18.4%) found in a 2014 study [51]. In a German study, around one third of the normal persons interviewed reported dyspeptic symptoms, including acute dyspepsia in 6.5% and chronic dyspepsia in 22.5% of cases [52]. 8%-30% and 8%-23% of Asian people suffer from of uninvestigated dyspepsia and FD, respectively [53]. Dyspepsia prevalence was 30.4% in India, 5% in Scandinavian countries, 24% in Spain and 45% in Nigeria estimated [68]. Smoking might affect all gastrointestinal functions including those of the esophagus, stomach, and colon, resulting in susceptibility to several kinds of FGIDs including GERD, FD, and IBS [54]. Potential lifestyle factors associated with dyspepsia include tobacco, alcohol, and analgesic consumption. Furthermore, dietary habits that include consumption of smoked food, fast food, salty food, coffee/tea, and spicy food were associated with aggravating the symptoms of dyspepsia; while fruits, vegetables, and water were noted to improve the symptoms [68]. FD is more prevalent in women (24.4%) than men (16.6%) and its occurrence was found to increase significantly with age [69, 70]. Typical dyspeptic symptoms include postprandial fullness, early satiety, epigastric pain, and epigastric burning [55]. Visceral hypersensitivity, impaired gastric accommodation and impaired gastric emptying are commonly reported by patients with functional dyspepsia. Involvement of duodenal hypersensitivity to the luminal contents, small bowel dysmotility, psychological disturbances, central nervous system disorders and *Helicobacter pylori* infection also been reported [56]. Delayed gastric emptying has been reported by gastric scintigraphy in a large proportion (up to 45%) of dyspeptic patients, especially those with PDS [57]. About 30–70% of the patients with functional dyspepsia experience delayed gastric emptying [86]. The overall costs to the health service associated with managing dyspepsia are considerable, estimated to be over \$18 billion per annum in the United States. Moreover, when one considers that dyspepsia impacts on physical, mental, and social aspects of health-related quality of life, the true overall costs to society are likely to be far higher, and also encompass loss of economic productivity due to sickness-related absence from work [58-60]. The risk of malignancy predominantly relates to increasing age, and so guidelines have previously recommended upper GI endoscopy to routinely investigate dyspepsia only when patients are aged 55 years and older [61]. The prevalence of functional dyspepsia (after normal upper endoscopy) is 12-15% in patients with IBS [64].

Exhibit 2. Alarm features in patients with dyspepsia [61]

- Age > 55 years with new onset dyspepsia*
- Evidence of overt gastrointestinal bleeding including melaena or haematemesis
- Dysphagia, particularly if progressive, and odynophagia
- Persistent vomiting
- Unintentional weight loss
- Palpable abdominal or epigastric mass or abnormal adenopathy
- Family history of upper gastrointestinal cancer
- Evidence of iron deficiency anemia after blood testing

* ACG/CAG guidelines now recommend an age threshold of 60 years or older.

Figure 2. Diagnostic algorithm of Helicobacter pylori-associated dyspepsia.

Patients with dyspeptic symptoms after negative routine laboratory and upper gastrointestinal endoscopy except for positive *H. pylori* tests, should undergo eradication therapy. If sustained symptomatic relief is obtained, their dyspeptic symptoms are considered as *H. pylori*-associated dyspepsia. On the other hand, if dyspeptic symptoms do not resolve or recur after eradication therapy, they are judged to have functional dyspepsia. EGD, oesophagastroduodenoscopy (Source: Sugano K, Tack J, Kuipers EJ on behalf of faculty members of Kyoto Global Consensus Conference, et al Kyoto global consensus report on Helicobacter pylori gastritis Gut 2015;64:1353-1367).

4.1. Rationale of Alternative Treatments with Dyspepsia

Prokinetics are recommended for the treatment of functional dyspepsia (FD) but systematic reviews give conflicting results on the efficacy of these agents [62]. Although several PPI-related adverse effects have been reported, their clinical relevance is not yet clear. Again, their beneficial effects for functional dyspepsia have not been fully confirmed [63]. The popularity of CAM in treating FGIDs has steadily increased in Western countries. In community settings, almost 50% of patients with FGIDs used CAM therapies. Herbal remedies consist of multi-component preparations, whose mechanisms of action have not been systematically clarified. Few studies analyzed the effectiveness of acupuncture in Western countries, yielding conflicting results and possibly reflecting a population bias of this treatment. Hypnosis has been extensively used in irritable bowel syndrome, but few data support its role in treating FD [67].

Exhibit 3. Adverse Events Reported in Patients Treated with Proton Pump Inhibitors [63], [84]	
Adverse events unrelated to acid inhibition	Adverse events related to acid inhibition
Allergic reaction to drug chemicals	Pneumonia
Collagenous colitis	Gastrointestinal infection
Acute interstitial nephritis	Gastric carcinoid tumor
Chronic kidney disease	Gastric fundic mucosal hypertrophy
Drug interaction	Changes in gut microbiome
Dementia	Small intestinal bacterial overgrowth
Cerebral ischemic diseases	Iron deficiency
Ischemic cardiac diseases	Bone fracture; decrease calcium absorption; Vitamin B12 deficiency; Hypomagnesemia; Gastric fundic gland polyps; Gastric & Colon cancer; Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis; Hepatic encephalopathy; Drug interaction

4.2. Herbs and Probiotics for Dyspepsia

Flavonoid rich phytochemical composition of the root extract of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, revealed significant decrease in symptoms scores of dyspepsia [71]. Adjuvant supplementation of honey-based formulation of Black Seed/ black caraway (*Nigella sativa*) can cause significant symptomatic improvement of patients with functional dyspepsia whom received the standard anti-secretory therapy [72]. Basil Leaf (*Ocimum basilicum* L.) strengthens stomach, nervous system and is also carminative, also has been demonstrated to decrease acid and pepsin outputs, widely used as a spice and a typical ingredient of the healthy Mediterranean diet [73,74]. The fruit of Amla (*Phyllanthus emblica* L.) has cytoprotective acid-reducing features, prevents indigestion, and controls acidity and well tolerated [75-77]. *Pistacia lentiscus* Desf. (Mastaki) act against different microorganisms (Mastic gum) specially *Helicobacter pylori*, positively affect liver function, could be effective as an alternative regime in patients unwilling to undergo eradication with the triple therapy regime [78,79]. Rhizome of Ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) is stomach tonic, protective, antiulcer and is effective for digestion problems, bloating, and nausea, stimulated gastric emptying and antral contractions in patients with functional dyspepsia [80-83]. Iberogast (commercial preparation of 9 herbal extracts including bitter candy tuft, lemon balm leaf, chamomile flower, caraway fruit, licorice root, angelica root, milk thistle fruit, peppermint leaf, and greater celandine herb) has been shown to protect against the development of ulcers with decreased acid production, increased mucin production, an increase in prostaglandin E2 release, both safe and effective for treatment of functional dyspepsia and IBS in Children [21]. Licorice root, the dried rhizome or extracts of *glycyrrhiza glabra*, has long been used in botanical medicine for treatment of gastric inflammation, showed a significant decrease in total symptom scores ($p < 0.05$) and improvement in quality of life with functional dyspepsia [77]. Red pepper as a drug is given in atonic dyspepsia and flatulence due to increasing the motility in the gastric antrum, duodenum, proximal jejunum and colon. It can also increase parietal, pepsin, and bile acid secretions. Chillies are known to protect against gastrointestinal ailments including dyspepsia, loss of appetite, gastroesophageal reflux disease and gastric ulcer due to the several mechanisms such as reducing the food transition time through the gastrointestinal tract and anti-*Helico pylori* effects [85]. Celery (*Apiumgraveolens*), radish (*Raphinussativus* L.), rocket (*Eruka sativa*), and marjoram (*Origanum majorana* L.) demonstrated anti-ulcer effect in experimental investigations [86]. Probiotics appear effective in the treatment of FD through the normalization of gastric microbiota. The finding of an FD-type phylum profile can be used to characterize patients with FD and may serve as an objective biomarker for both the diagnosis and treatment of FD. Probiotics could be effective treatment for the indigestion via the reduction of *Escherichia/Shigella*, major source of toxic lipopolysaccharides in the upper GIT [98].

5. Constipation

Constipation is a common gastrointestinal problem, which causes many expenses for the community with an estimated prevalence of 1% to 80%, worldwide. Various factors are involved in the pathogenesis of the disease, including type of diet, genetic predisposition, colonic motility, absorption, social economic status, daily behaviors, and biological and pharmaceutical factors. Acute constipation may cause closure of the intestine, which may even require surgery. Chronic constipation is a complicated condition among older individuals, which is characterized by difficult stool passage [87]. To better characterize the condition, physicians conceive constipation objectively using defecation frequency, with a normal range of between three and 21 bowel movements per week [94]. Factors that may contribute to functional constipation include pain, fever,

dehydration, dietary and fluid intake, psychological issues, toilet training, medicines, and family history of constipation [88]. Pathogenesis is multifactorial with focusing on the type of diet, genetic predisposition, colonic motility, and absorption, as well as behavioral, biological, and pharmaceutical factors. Furthermore, low fiber dietary intake, inadequate water intake, sedentary lifestyle, IBS, failure to respond to urge to defecate, and slow transit have been revealed to be associated with predisposition [87,90]. About 30% of the general population experiences problems with constipation during life time. with elderly people and women being mostly affected. Constipation is also reported to occur in 2% to 25% of healthy people, but the incidence sometimes rises to 80% in critically ill patients [101].

Figure 3. Initial management of acute primary constipation (symptoms <3 months) (Source: Constipation in adults: Treatment Practice. BMJ Best Practice).

When constipation presents acutely, it is important to consider possible secondary causes, including colorectal cancer. Further investigations may be performed to exclude secondary causes. Enemas, suppositories, large volume polyethylene glycol solution (PEG), stimulant laxatives, or disimpaction with sedation may be required if there is fecal impaction. If fecal impaction is absent and secondary causes are excluded, the treatment is the same as for patients with chronic constipation. Initial steps in the management of chronic primary constipation are: Patient education; Lifestyle modifications; High-fiber diet; Increased fluid; Regular exercise; Bulk laxatives. Dietary and lifestyle changes may be helpful. Patients are advised to increase their daily dietary fiber and calorie intake (in patients with low caloric intake). Patients are advised on adequate fluid intake and encouraged to get regular nonstrenuous exercise. Modest exercise can help relieve constipation, especially if patients are sedentary or generally inactive. Patients are advised to dedicate time for bowel movements and to avoid postponing bowel movements when an urge for defecation is felt.

Exhibit 4. Common causes of secondary constipation[90]	
Drugs	Anabolic steroids, analgesics, opioids (codeine), NSAIDs, anticholinergics, anticonvulsivants, antidepressants, antihistamines, antihypertensives (verapamil e clonidine), anti-Parkinsonian, diuretics, antacids containing calcium or aluminium, cholestyramine.
Neuropathic and myopathic disorders	Amyloidosis, Chagas disease, connective tissue disorders, CNS lesions, autonomic diabetic neuropathy, Hirschprung's disease, multiple sclerosis.
Idiopathic	Paraneoplastic syndromes, Parkinson's disease, dementia, scleroderma, post-viral colon-paresis, intestinal pseudo-obstruction, spinal or ganglion tumor, ischemia.
Electrolytic balance alterations	Hypokalemia, hypercalcemia
Organic intestinal diseases	Obstruction/stenosis: adenoma, cancer, diverticulitis, rectocele, hernia, foreign bodies, faecal impaction, IBD and complications.
	Anorectal abnormalities: anal stenosis or fissures, proctitis, rectocele, haemorrhoids.
Endocrine-metabolic causes	Hypothyroidism, diabetes mellitus, pregnancy and childbirth, dehydration, low fibers intake diet, hyperglycemia

5.1. Prevalence and Economic Burden

Functional constipation is a prevalent condition in childhood, about 29.6% worldwide. Up to 84% of functionally constipated children suffer from fecal incontinence, while more than one-third of children present with behavioral problems primary or secondary due to constipation [88]. However, only a minority of patients (approximately 25 %) uses medical treatments, whereas a considerable proportion relies on alternative solutions, following advices given in pharmacies or herbalist's shops [91,92]. A population-based study of outpatient clinic and emergency department visits found outpatients taking five or more drugs had an 88% increased risk of experiencing an adverse drug effect compared to those who were taking fewer drugs [93]. According to reports from Western countries, the prevalence of CC in the general population ranges from 2% to 28%, with an increasing trend over years. Moreover, severe constipation is frequently observed in elderly women, with rates of 2 to 3 times higher than that of their male counterparts [95]. FGIDs, including chronic constipation (CC), are among the most frequent illnesses seen by gastroenterologists and account for up to one-half of patient care time (1). CC is a remarkably common and costly condition that can negatively impact the QoL, and result in a major social and economic burden [96]. 66,287 people in the UK were admitted to hospital with constipation as the main condition in 2014/15, equivalent to 182 people a day. 48,409 were unplanned e emergencyadmissions (this is equivalent to 13 3 per day). The total cost to hospitals for treating unplanned admissions due to constipation was £145 million in 2014/15. The figure is likely to be much higher for total NHS expenditure on constipation when including GP visits, home visits and prescriptions. The prescription cost of laxative costs is £101 million (Over the counter costs of laxatives will undoubtedly be higher). 1 in 7 adults are affected by constipation at any one time in UK [97]. Pregnancy predisposes women to developing constipation owing to physiologic and anatomic changes in the gastrointestinal tract. For instance, rising progesterone levels during pregnancy and reduced motilin hormone levels lead to increases in bowel transit time. Also, there is increased water absorption from the intestines, which causes stool to dry out. Decreased maternal activity and increased vitamin supplementation (eg, iron and calcium) can further contribute to constipation. Later in pregnancy, an enlarging uterus might slow onward movement of feces. Constipation can result in serious complications such as fecal impaction, but such complications are rare [107].

5.2. Herbs and Probiotics for Constipation

Cascara sagrada used (hydroxyanthraquinone glycosides found in the dried bark) to be approved by the U.S. FDA as an OTC drug for constipation. However, over the years, concerns were raised about its safety and effectiveness (causes nausea, vomiting and griping abdominal pain) [98-100]. Psyllium is the most commonly used bulking agent in Canada. In placebo-control trials, psyllium has been shown to decrease stool transit time, and improve stool frequency, consistency and weight; when psyllium was compared with lactulose, the magnitude of effects on stool frequency was similar, associated benefit of dietary fiber in reducing coronary heart disease and lowering low-density lipoprotein cholesterol, it is generally recommended as the initial conservative treatment for chronic constipation [100]. Recently, maintenance of intestinal motility has become an important issue in intensive-care medicine. Although drugs such as metoclopramide, erythromycin,

neostigmine, and others are reported to resolve incompetent intestinal motility [101], there are problems with drug tolerance. Rhubarb has been widely used as a traditional Chinese herbal medicine since ancient times. Sennoside A and other dianthrone derivatives are reported to be the active ingredients causing rhubarb's laxative effect. To induce its laxative effect, rhubarb needs to be metabolized to rhein anthrone by β -glucosidase, which is produced by gut microbiota [102]. Improvement in intestinal motility can prevent sepsis of gut origin [103]. Rhubarb contains dianthrone glucosides (sennosides A to F) and anthraquinones (e.g., rhein, aloe-emodin, emodin, physcion, chrysophanol); Among these components, sennosides (i.e., stimulant laxatives), have been well documented for their pharmacological action on constipation [104]. Senna is used to treat constipation and clear the bowel before some medical procedures. It should only be used in the short term and at the recommended doses. Long-term and high-dose use has been reported to cause liver damage [105]. Senna induced dermatitis is rare, but may occur when patients need a higher dose. Pediatric caregivers should advise families of the rare side effect of skin blistering and educate them to change the diaper frequently in children who are not toilet-trained to reduce stool to skin exposure. Senna is a safe treatment option for constipation in children [106]. Until more data are available, the use of probiotics for the treatment of constipation should be considered investigational. Current ESPGHAN/NASPGHAN recommendations that probiotics should not be used in the treatment of functional constipation in children [113]. The bacterial endotoxin lipopolysaccharide may influence intestinal motility by delaying gastric emptying and inducing sphincter dysfunction. Human colonic gases produced by microflora may also be associated with changes in gut motility. For example, breath methane excretion in patients with slow-transit constipation was greater than in healthy subjects or patients with normal-transit constipation, supporting the idea that methane can slow gut transit. Collectively, the altered intestinal microbiota may play an essential role in the pathogenesis of chronic constipation [114].

Exhibit 5. Summary of randomized controlled trials of probiotics for the management of chronic constipation [114]

Population	Intervention	Comparator	Author's conclusion
n = 159 (control n = 80, intervention n = 79)	<i>B. lactis</i> DN-173 010	Acidified milk without probiotics	Increased stool frequency, but not statistically significant compared with control group
n = 44 (control n = 22, intervention n = 22)	<i>L. reuteri</i> DSM 17938	Identical placebo	Increased bowel frequency
n = 30 (control n = 15, intervention n = 15)	<i>B. lactis</i> Bi-07	Fresh cheese without probiotics	Beneficial effects
n = 126 (control n = 63, intervention n = 63)	<i>B. lactis</i> DN-173010	Acidified milk without probiotics	Beneficial effects on stool frequency, defecation condition and stool consistency
n = 17 (cross-over design)	<i>B. lactis</i> GCL2505	Milk-like drink	Beneficial effects
n = 100 (control n = 34, Intervention: high dose n = 33 low dose n = 33)	<i>B. lactis</i> HN019	Capsules with rice maltodextrin	Decreased whole gut transit time in a dose-dependent manner
n = 90 (control n = 43, intervention n = 47)	<i>L. casei</i> Shirota	Fermented milk without probiotics	Improvement in constipation severity
n = 20 (cross-over design)	<i>L. paracasei</i> IMPC 2.1	Artichokes without probiotics	Beneficial effects
n = 70 (control n = 35, intervention n = 35)	<i>L. casei</i> shirota	Beverage without probiotics	Beneficial effects on self-reported severity of constipation and stool consistency

5.3. Herbs in Pregnancy Induced Constipation

It has been estimated that approximately 11% to 38% of pregnant women experience constipation, which is generally described as infrequent bowel movements or difficult evacuation [107]. The prevalence of herbal medicine utilization in pregnancy ranges between 7% and 55% in different geographical, social and cultural settings, and ethnic groups [108]. The majority of the studies reported the highest use of herbs during the first trimester with the frequency varying from 17.3% to 67.5% in Middle East [107]. It is a well-documented fact that the risk in pregnancy is unknown for 91.2% of the approved medications. The use of herbal products which

are not usually tested in clinical trials during pregnancy could result in immense risk to the mother and fetus [109,110]. Since herbal medicines are a part of traditional medicine, they are not included in the FDA pregnancy categories giving a false impression of safety. The whole extracts of these herbal drugs contain numerous active molecules that could elicit adverse effects including teratogenicity [111,112].

6. Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS)

IBS is present in patients with symptoms of chronic abdominal pain and altered bowel habits but no identifiable organic etiology [113]. Patients with IBS often associate their symptoms to certain foods [115]. In CSID, recessive mutations in the SI gene (coding for the disaccharidase digesting sucrose and 60% of dietary starch) cause clinical features of IBS through colonic accumulation of undigested carbohydrates, triggering bowel symptoms [116]. Diagnosing IBS can be challenging due to the nonspecific nature of symptoms, overlapping upper and lower abdominal symptoms, and the frequent presence of somatic and psychological comorbidities. Despite these guidelines, there remains low awareness and little consensus on the use of diagnostic tests and surgical procedures in IBS. Furthermore, although surgery has no role in the recommended treatment approach for IBS, multiple studies have reported that this patient population is predisposed to unnecessary surgical procedures, suggesting a disconnect between the recommended best practices and real-world management of IBS [117]. Under certain ambiguous circumstances, an exclusive and pure diagnosis of IBS cannot be achieved because of food-dependent symptoms: in fact, up to 80% of IBS patients identify food as a possible trigger for their symptoms, so they increasingly ask for dietary and behavioral counseling [118]. Common practices for IBS management begin with diet and lifestyle modification, and in more severe cases, pharmacotherapy (e.g. antidepressants, smooth muscle antispasmodics, or secretagogues) [119].

Figure 4. Clinical overlap between IBS and IBS-like disorders.

IBS; FODMAPs; SIBO; NCGS; ATIs; Ni ACM. FODMAPs have been shown to share clinical characteristics and trigger foods with both lactose intolerance and Ni ACM. Specifically, many foods rich in FODMAPs are also high in lactose. Given the high prevalence of lactose intolerance, it is not surprising that a diet low in FODMAPs may reduce or even resolve gastrointestinal and extra-intestinal symptoms. The same thing can be true for foods rich in Ni, very numerous in the FODMAPs family, such as pears, cabbage, garlic, onion and legumes. Another important intersection exists between FODMAPs and NCGS, or even better between Ni ACM and NCGS: upon closer analysis, symptoms of suspected NCGS patients are actually triggered by associated Ni-rich ingredients or condiments (e.g. yeast or tomato), and not by gluten itself. As a consequence, foods such as bread, pasta with tomato sauce, pizza and bakery products turn into real traps for Ni-sensitive and/or lactose intolerant patients, in defiance of the Mediterranean diet, recently declared part of the UNESCO's Intangible Heritage List.

6.1. Prevalence and Economic burden

IBS affects both men and women of all ages. It is thought only a fraction of individuals with symptoms of IBS seek medical attention. The prevalence of IBS globally is 11%, however, it is thought that IBS often remains underdiagnosed. A survey of patients with IBS (both with and without a formal diagnosis) conducted by the Gastrointestinal Society in Canada showed that 46% had missed work or school due to IBS symptoms [120]. Its estimated prevalence is 10%–20%, although marked variation may exist based on geographical location; for example, its prevalence is 21% in South America versus 7% in Southeast Asia. It is nearly twice more common in women than men [118]. Various studies have reported prevalence to be approximately 8 to 12% in children, and 5 to 17% in adolescents [125]. IBS causes a significant burden on healthcare systems, due in part to the high level of HRU associated with IBS. Direct medical costs attributed to IBS in the US, excluding prescription and OTC medicines, were estimated at US \$1.5–\$10 billion per year in 2005. According to University at Buffalo, the economic burden of IBS in the U.S. is estimated at \$28 billion annually [124]. A portion of these costs may be related to unnecessary and high-frequency tests, although few studies have assessed the factors underlying frequent tests and procedures among patients with IBS [117]. In IBS, it has been reported that 50% to 90% of patients have or had at some point one or more common psychiatric condition, including major depressive disorder, generalized anxiety disorder, social phobia, somatization disorder, or posttraumatic stress disorder [123].

Exhibit 6. Subtypes of IBS are recognized by the Rome IV criteria based on the person's reported predominant bowel habit, when not on medications [118], [120-122]	
IBS-C	With predominant constipation. The symptoms most frequently reported for IBS-C are: abdominal pain, bloating and constipation. 32% of IBS-C respondents reported feeling depressed because of their condition almost every day in the previous month. HRQoL for those with IBS-C is low compared to those with chronic conditions such as diabetes, heart failure and heart defects, who have a high rate of mortality, and also those with asthma, migraine and rheumatoid arthritis, with well-known morbidity.
IBS-D	With predominant diarrhea. The symptoms most frequently reported for IBS-D are: abdominal pain and discomfort, abdominal bloating, distension, urgency and diarrhea. 47% of respondents with IBS-D stated that they had little or no ability to predict their symptoms on a daily basis. When asked how IBS-D affects them, 81% stated that they avoided situations where there was no nearby washroom.
IBS-M	With both constipation and diarrhea. In the United States, patients are equally distributed among IBS with diarrhea (IBS-D), IBS with constipation (IBS-C), and IBS with a mixed bowel pattern (IBS-M), whereas in Europe, studies have found either IBS-C (45.9%) or IBS-D (50%) as the main pattern group. IBS-M is a heterogeneous symptom group and thus requires that subclassification criteria be better defined. Use of laxative/antidiarrheal medications adds to the diagnostic complexity in a potentially more severe subset of IBS-M and should be assessed for accurate subclassification.
IBS-U	Un-subtyped IBS, has a lower prevalence (17.8%). Un-subtyped IBS subjects had the highest HR-QOL compared to other subtypes.

6.2. Lifestyle Modification

An important lifestyle adjustment that should be recommended to IBS patients is regular exercise. Mild exercise or physical activity has been shown to reduce IBS symptoms and alleviates bloating and gas production in several studies. Since regular exercise also helps to increase gastrointestinal motility it is beneficial in IBS-C patients with primary low GI movement and hard stools. As part of exercise, yoga has been investigated due to its low impact on joints and its relatively targeted postures that can help to reduce GI symptoms. Pranayama yoga administered twice daily has been shown to increase sympathetic tone and may benefit IBS-D patients that present with decreased sympathetic activity to the same degree than daily loperamide administration in the control group [127]. Fiber is defined as non-starch polysaccharides in agreement with FAO/WHO/DOH measurement methods. It includes β -glucans, pectins, gums, mucilages and some hemicelluloses. Dietary sources include oats, psyllium, ispaghula, nuts and seeds, some fruit and vegetables and pectins. An increase in fiber has often been suggested as an initial treatment for IBS [131].

Figure 5. IBS Dietary Treatment Pathway.

In the last 10 years, evidence has emerged for the restriction of a group of short chain fermentable carbohydrates which have collectively become known as FODMAPs. The common factor in these foods is the size and chain length of these carbohydrate molecules, as they all contain between 1 and 10 glucose molecules. This group of short-chain carbohydrates is susceptible to colonic fermentation by a number of possible mechanisms, which have been shown to exacerbate IBS symptoms. There is strong evidence to support three mechanisms of action: 1. Augmentation of small intestinal water 2. Increased colonic fermentation 3. Immune modulation (Source: Jankovich E, Watkins A. Case Study: The low FODMAP diet reduced symptoms in a patient with endometriosis and IBS. S Afr J Clin Nutr 2017;30(4):32-36).

6.3. Herbs and Probiotics for IBS

Pharmacological treatment of IBS varies from antidepressants including tricyclic antidepressants and selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, to antispasmodics, 5-HT₃ antagonists, 5-HT₄ agonists, antibiotics, probiotics, and melatonin. But involvement of numerous factors in pathophysiology and a very significant placebo effect cause therapy of this disease to be more complex. Due to disappointing results with conventional IBS treatments, complementary and alternative medicines are becoming attractive options for many patients [126]. CAM alone and in conjunction with pharmacological treatments as an integrative approach to manage patients with IBS and improve their quality of life. Prokinetics are not specific to IBS and increase gastrointestinal motility in general by acting via dopamine and 5-HT₃ receptors as antagonists or 5-HT₄ receptors as agonists. Lubiprostone, a 5-HT₄ agonist, has been recently approved to treat IBS-C in women through activation of chloride channels leading to increased water secretion into the lumen which decreased transit time and associated visceral pain in patients. The common use of 5-HT₃ receptor antagonists such as ondansetron and granisetron to reduce visceral pain perception in IBS-D patients has shown some benefits but is also limited by side effects [127]. Novartis has agreed to continue to supply Zelnorm® (Tegaserod maleate) for use in emergency situations, due to an increased cardiovascular risk [128,129]. Glaxo Wellcome (Now GSK) has informed the US FDA that it will voluntarily withdraw Lotronex® (alosetron) tablets (for IBS-D) from the market [130]. Clinical benefits of supposed spasmolytic (anti-spasmodic) agents may relate more to effects on visceral sensation than motility. A mixture of dried powdered slippery elm bark, lactulose, oat bran, and licorice root significantly improved both bowel habit and IBS symptoms in patients with constipation-predominant IBS [132]. There is a growing body of evidence which indicates therapeutic properties for ALE. Furthermore, 96% of patients rated ALE as better than or at least equal to previous therapies administered for their symptoms, and the tolerability of ALE was very good [133]. In IBS, the gastrointestinal flora may undergo both qualitative and quantitative changes and the most common finding is a decrease in the population of 'good bacteria' such as *Bifidobacteria* and *Lactobacilli* and the faecal microflora has increased numbers of facultative organisms. Probiotics may be useful in the management of IBS, however dose and specific bacterial strain are important. In vivo studies have identified some of the variables that determine the survival of probiotics through the GI tract, and some have attempted to quantify the degree of survival of the dose administered. This was found to vary from 10 to 50% depending on the probiotic species used and the dose administered [131].

Exhibit 7. Herbs used for treatment of irritable bowel syndrome [125],[127]		
Herbal medicine	Type of study	Results
Artichoke (Whole plant)	Post-marketing surveillance study	Significant reductions in the severity of symptoms
	Open dose-ranging study	“Alternating constipation/diarrhea” toward “normal”, significant improvement in total quality-of-life (QOL) score
Fumaria officinalis (Whole plant)	Double-blind, placebo-RCT	No difference between treatment and placebo groups
Curcuma longa (Rhizome)	Pilot study, partially blinded, RCT randomized,	No difference between treatment and placebo groups
Iberogast®	Randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled	Significantly improves quality of life and reduces abdominal pain in IBS patients
Hypericum perforatum (HP) (Aerial parts)	Open-label, uncontrolled trial	Autonomic nervous system to different stressor, improvement of Gastrointestinal symptoms of IBS
	Double-blind, placebo-RCT	No difference between treatment and placebo groups
Mentha piperita (MP) (Oil/Essence)	Double-blind, placebo-RCT	Peppermint-oil was effective and well tolerated
	Prospective double-blind, placebo-RCT	Improves abdominal symptoms
	Double-blind, placebo-RCT	Significantly improved the quality of life, improves abdominal symptoms
Plantago psyllium (Seed)	Placebo, RCT	Decrease Symptom severity significantly in the psyllium group, no differences in QOL
Carmint (Mentha spicata leaf, Melissa officinalis leaf, Coriandrum sativum fruit)	Double-blind, placebo-RCT	Severity and frequency of abdominal pain/discomfort were significantly lower in the Carmint group than the placebo group

7. Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD)

IBS, a common gastrointestinal disorder involving the gut-brain axis; IBD, a chronic relapsing inflammatory disorder. Both have significant overlap in terms of symptoms, pathophysiology, and treatment, suggesting the possibility of IBS and IBD being a single disease entity albeit at opposite ends of the spectrum [133]. A significant association between IBD and later occurrence of PD, which is consistent with recent basic scientific findings of a potential role of GI inflammation in development of parkinsonian disorders [134]. An area of recent research interest where the role of adiposity is avidly discussed is in IBD, which presents mainly as Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC) [135]. IBD is a chronic illness, and sexual dysfunction is a well-recognized complication of chronic illness [136]. A subgroup of IBD patients considered diet to be a more important and successful managing tool than medication to relieve their disease symptoms [137].

Figure 6. Environmental triggers in IBD.

A wide variety of environmental triggers have been associated with IBD pathogenesis, including the gut microbiota, diet, pollution and early-life factors. Smoking remains the most widely studied and replicated risk factor, contributing to increased risk and severity of CD while conferring protection against UC. Lower plasma vitamin D is associated with an increased risk of Crohn's disease, and vitamin D supplementation may prevent relapse of disease. Several medications including oral contraceptives, post-menopausal hormone replacement, aspirin, NSAIDs, and antibiotics may increase risk of CD or UC with the mechanisms of effect remaining inadequately defined. There is continuing evidence that depression and psychosocial stress may play a role in the pathogenesis of both CD and UC, while at the same time also increasing risk for disease flares. There is also a growing understanding of the role of diet on IBD, in particular through its effect on the microbiome. Animal protein intake and n-6 fatty acids may increase risk of UC while n-3 fatty acids and dietary fiber may confer protection. The effect of diet on established disease remains poorly studied. There is need for routine measurement of a spectrum of environmental exposures in prospective studies to further our understanding (Source: Ananthakrishnan AN. Environmental triggers for inflammatory bowel disease. *Curr Gastroenterol Rep.* 2013;15(1):302).

7.1. Prevalence and Economic Burden of IBD

IBD, including UC and CD, are chronic, disabling, and progressive disorders characterized by lifelong treatment and whose incidences are increasing in Asia [141]. EIMs of IBD occur in up to 55% of patients with CD and 35% of those with UC. Although arthritis/arthralgia is the most common EIM in both disorders, multiple organs may be affected including skin, eye and liver [145]. Approximately 2.5 million–3 million people in Europe are affected by IBD. The highest rates of IBD are reported in Scandinavia and the UK. The incidence and prevalence of UC in the UK is estimated to be 14 cases per 100,000 person-years and 244 cases per 100,000 people, respectively. The incidence and prevalence of CD in the UK is estimated to be 7–11 per 100,000 and 85–145 cases per 100,000 people, respectively [144]. An increasing number of these children are being treated with immunosuppressive and biological medications. Although these medications can improve the short-term outcome and quality of life of children with IBD, they have been associated with opportunistic infections, malignancy, and lymphoproliferative disorders among IBD populations. It is estimated that 15% to 20% of all cases of IBD are diagnosed in the childhood and adolescent period [146]. Patients with IBD have a 2- to 3-fold increased risk of colorectal cancer death; therefore, colorectal cancer surveillance via colonoscopy is recommended for IBD patients [147]. Environmental factors probably have a major role in IBD; antibiotic use, childbirth mode, breastfeeding, air pollution, NSAID use, hypoxia or high altitude, diet and urban environments have been studied [148].

7.2. Rationale of DS and Probiotics in IBD

A recent survey by de Vries et al., 2019, DS were used by 68% of the IBD patients. Although over 71% had received dietary advice mainly by dietitians, 81% stated that the main source of their nutritional knowledge related to IBD was their own experience [137]. Despite recent advancements, Crohn's disease and ulcerative

colitis remain chronic and progressive diseases. One of the primary reasons for persistent inflammation and bowel damage is failure of medical therapy. With growing therapeutic options, there is an increased temptation to quickly move to the next therapy and label the prior therapy as a failure; however, this can lead to inadequate optimization of medications and poor control of disease. On the other hand, failure to recognize ongoing mucosal inflammation despite optimized treatment and moving to the next agent can lead to progression of disease and long-term complications [138]. Anti-tumor necrosis factor antibodies have led to a revolution in the treatment of IBD; however, a sizable proportion of patients does not respond to therapy. There is increasing evidence suggesting that treatment failure may be classified as mechanistic (pharmacodynamic), pharmacokinetic, or immune-mediated. Data regarding the contribution of these factors in children with IBD treated with infliximab (IFX) are still incomplete [139]. Endoscopic therapy has been explored and used in the management of strictures, fistulas/abscesses, colitis-associated neoplasia, postsurgical acute or chronic leaks, and obstructions [140]. For several decades, medical treatments for IBD were limited to non-biological therapies (i.e., aminosalicylates, thiopurines, and steroids), which provide symptomatic improvement but do not change the disease course [141]. Anti-TNF agents (infliximab, adalimumab, and certolizumab) have reduced the need for surgery and hospitalization and have improved the quality of life of patients by changing the course of the disease. Thus, guidelines recommend the use of anti-TNF agents initially in moderate-to-severe IBD or if non-biological therapy fails. However, these treatments have not been effective in all patients, and patients who initially responded to treatment have also lost their responsiveness over time. Furthermore, although anti-TNF agents are generally well tolerated, their use is associated with adverse effects, including risks of infection and malignancies [142,143].

7.3. Use of Herbs and Probiotics

The use of herbal therapy in IBD is increasing worldwide. It can be assumed that the efficacy of herbal therapies in IBD is promising. The most important clinical trials conducted so far refer to the use of mastic gum, tormentil extracts, wormwood herb, *Triticum aestivum*, germinated barley foodstuff, and *Boswellia serrata*. In ulcerative colitis, *Triticum aestivum*, *Andrographis paniculata* extract and topical Xilei-san were superior to placebo in inducing remission or clinical response, and curcumin was superior to placebo in maintaining remission; *Boswellia serrata* gum resin and *Plantago ovata* seeds were as effective as mesalazine, whereas *Oenothera biennis* had similar relapse rates as ω -3 fatty acids in the treatment of ulcerative colitis. In Crohn's disease, mastic gum, *Artemisia absinthium*, and *Tripterygium wilfordii* were superior to placebo in inducing remission and preventing clinical postoperative recurrence, respectively [149].

Exhibit 7. Herbs used for treatment of IBD			
Herbal medicine	Type of study	Ref No.	Results
<i>Triticum aestivum</i> (Poaceae)	randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study	150	Treatment was associated with significant reduction in the overall disease activity index and in the severity of rectal bleeding. Apart from nausea, no other serious side effects were noticed
<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Randomized, double-blind multicentre study	151	Compared with Mesalazine (4.5 mg/day), there were no significant differences between the two treated groups when considering the clinical efficacy rates or the safety profile
<i>Boswellia serrata</i> (Burseraceae)	Single Centered study	152	Compared with Sulfasalazine, all parameters tested improved after treatment with <i>Boswellia serrata</i> gum in 82% patients
<i>Artemisia absinthium</i>	Randomized, double-blind multicentre study	153	Compared with placebo, after 8 weeks of treatment with wormwood, there was almost complete remission of symptoms in 65% of the patients,
<i>Tripterygium wilfordii</i> Hook F (TWHF)	Randomized controlled trials	154	Patients receiving mesalazine experienced less adverse events, but no significant difference was found about ADEs resulted withdrawal in the 3 groups. In addition, compared with low-dose TwHF and mesalazine, the authors also detected significant superiority of high-dose TwHF arm in the decrease of CDAI and SESCO
Evening primrose oil <i>Oenothera biennis</i>	Randomized controlled trials	155	<i>Oenothera biennis</i> had similar relapse rates as omega-3 fatty acids in the treatment of UC

Altered gut bacteria and bacterial metabolic pathways are two important factors in initiation and progression of IBD. However, efficacy of probiotics in remission of patients with IBD has not been characterized [156]. Among the effects claimed for probiotics are beneficial immunomodulation, reduction of serum cholesterol, improved lactose digestion and protection against colon cancer [157,158]. Probiotic administration improved the clinical symptoms, histological alterations, and mucus production in most of the evaluated animal studies, but some results suggest that caution should be taken when administering these agents in the relapse stages of IBD [158]. In CD, the entire gastrointestinal tract can be involved and the inflammation can extend through the intestinal wall from mucosa to serosa. Areas of inflammation may be interspersed with relatively normal mucosa. In CD, the predominant symptoms are diarrhea, abdominal pain and weight loss whereas in UC diarrhea is the main symptom, often accompanied by rectal bleeding. Both diseases are common in the industrialized world, with highest incidences in North America and Northern Europe [159].

Exhibit 8. Summary of probiotic anti-inflammatory effects in In Vitro studies. [160]			
Cell Type	Probiotic Strain	Type of Study	Main Outcome
human DC	<i>L. casei</i> Shirota	In vitro	DC from UC patients samples have an increase of IL-4 production and loss of IL-22 and IFN- γ secretion. <i>L. casei</i> Shirota treatment restored the normal stimulatory capacity through a reduction in the TLR-2 and TLR4 expression
IPEC-J2 model	<i>L. plantarum</i> strain CGMCC1258	In vitro	<i>L. plantarum</i> decreased transcript abundances of IL-8, TNF- α , and negative regulators of TLRs. Moreover, <i>L. plantarum</i> treatment decreased the gene and protein expression of occludin
PIE cells	<i>L. delbrueckii</i> subsp. <i>delbrueckii</i> TUA4408L	In vitro	The activation of MAPK and NF- κ B pathways induced by <i>E. coli</i> 987P were downregulated through upregulation of TLR negative regulators, principally by TLR2
IEC-6	<i>E. coli</i> Nissle 1917 and <i>L. rhamnosus</i> GG	In vitro	Pre-treatment with these probiotics could prevent or inhibit enterocyte apoptosis and loss of intestinal barrier function induced by 5-FU
DC	<i>L. paracasei</i> CNCM I-4034, <i>B. breve</i> CNCM I-4035, and <i>L. rhamnosus</i> CNCM I-4036	In vitro	Induction of TLR-9 expression and TGF- β 2 secretion. CFS treatment decreased the pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines

8. Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD)

The presenting symptoms of PUD vary depending on the age of the patient. Hematemesis or melena is reported in up to half of patients with PUD. Infants and younger children usually present with feeding difficulty, vomiting, crying episodes, hematemesis, or melena [161]. The major symptom of uncomplicated PUD is upper abdominal dyspepsia such as bloating, early satiety, and nausea. *H. pylori* infection plays a crucial role in the pathogenesis of PUD. *H. pylori* infection is involved in various gastroduodenal pathologies, and evokes the production of proinflammatory interleukin-1 β , leading to the reduction of blood flow to the gastroduodenal tract and increasing the risk of peptic ulcers. *H. pylori* can colonize not only in the stomach, but also in the oral cavity. The oral cavity may be a reservoir for *H. pylori* and a potential source for infection of the stomach [162]. EGD is most accurate diagnostic test with sensitivity and specificity up to 90% in diagnosing gastric and duodenal ulcers. Surgical treatment is indicated if the patient is unresponsive to medical treatment, noncompliant or at high risk of complications. Surgical options include vagotomy or partial gastrectomy [163]. Factors that increase risk of developing peptic ulcer include smoking, older individuals, O blood type, and stress. Peptic ulcers that tend to heal longer than duodenal ulcer is at higher risk of developing gastritis and gastric malignancy [168]. Classically, patients with duodenal ulcers complain of worsening abdominal pain on an empty stomach and describe hunger or abdominal pain two to three hours after meals or at night. In contrast, patients with gastric ulcers report nausea, vomiting, weight loss and post-prandial abdominal pain. Elderly patients are often minimally symptomatic and some patients with untreated PUD may have intermittent symptoms due to spontaneous healing and then relapse due to persistence of risk factors, such as continued NSAIDs use or *H. pylori* infection [169].

8.1. Prevalence and Economic Burden of PUD

The prevalence of PUD ranges from 0.12 to 1.5% and increases with age [162]. *H. pylorus* is a gram-negative bacillus that is found within the gastric epithelial cells. This bacterium is responsible for 90% of duodenal ulcers and 70% to 90% of gastric ulcers, up to 85% of individuals infected with *H. pylori* are asymptomatic and have no complications [163], [165]. PUD is a global problem with a lifetime risk of development ranging from 5% to 10% [164]. In many studies worldwide (United States, Brazil and China), the prevalence of *H. pylori* among subjects with dyspepsia was 28.9%, 57%, and 84% respectively [165]. The prevalence differs in the world population between the duodenal and gastric ulcers, and the mean age of people with the disease is between 30 and 60 years, but it can happen in any age [166]. Environmental elements such as alcohol and nicotine can inhibit or reduce secretion of mucus and bicarbonate, increasing acid secretion. Genetic factors can influence, and children of parents with duodenal ulcer are three times more likely to have ulcer than the population [167]. 30% PUD patients are smoker [168]. NSAIDs account for over 90% of all ulcers and approximately 25% of NSAID users will develop peptic ulcer disease [169]. Approximately 500,000 persons develop PU in the United States each year [170]. Peptic ulcers accounted for 301,000 deaths in 2013, which is down from 327,000 deaths in 1990 [174]. Low socioeconomic status and concrete life difficulties are associated with peptic ulcer in the general population cross-sectionally and prospectively after adjustment for major physical risk factors, lending credence to a relationship between psychological stress and peptic ulcer [175].

8.2. Lifestyle Modification for PUD

The physicochemical properties of fiber fractions produce different physiological effects in the organism. Soluble fibers, found in apple, oatmeal, and pear are responsible, for instance, for an increased viscosity in the intestinal content. Insoluble fibers (whole grains, granola, flaxseed) increase stool bulk, reduce transit time in the large intestine, and make fecal elimination easier and quicker [171]. Physical activity has numerous health benefits and may also represent a cost-effective approach to the prevention of peptic ulcers. At the levels observed in this study among the moderately active group (walking or jogging <10 miles a week), possible adverse effects—for example, injuries—are minimized. In the general population, only about a third of adults undertake this much physical activity

Strategies to promote safe walking, jogging, and cycling may benefit many aspects of health in addition to the cardiovascular and musculoskeletal systems [173]. Moderate physical activity could have a favorable impact on a number of risk factors for peptic ulceration. It could reduce gastric secretions and enhance immune function, with the latter reducing the risk of *Helicobacter pylori* infection. Moderate activity might also reduce anxiety and encourage the adoption of a healthy lifestyle, with avoidance of smoking and an excessive consumption of alcohol. However, prolonged endurance exercise seems likely to have a negative impact, suppressing immune function, reducing mucosal blood flow, and calling for frequent administration of NSAIDs [176].

Exhibit 9. Allowed foods, foods that should be consumed with caution, and foods that must be avoided [172]			
Food groups	Allowed	Use with caution	Prohibited
Dairy	Milk, low-fat cheeses, yogurt, fermented milk	Fatty cheeses (mascarpone, cream cheese, gorgonzola)	-
Oilseeds	Flaxseed, Brazilian nut, walnuts	-	-
Oils and olive oils	Vegetable oils, olive oil	-	Fried foods
Fruits	Apple, papaya, melon, banana	Orange, pineapple, acerola, passion fruit	Lemon
Vegetables	Leafy dark green vegetables, carrot, beet, green bean, spinach, kale, radish, zucchini, leek	Broccoli, cauliflower, cabbage, cucumber, onion, red pepper	Spicy peppers (black pepper, chilies)
Legumes	Bean soup, lentils, chickpeas, soybean	Beans	-
Meats	Lean meat (beef, pork, chicken, fish)	Fatty meats, organ meats and sausages	-
Sweets	-	Concentrated sweets	Chocolate
Beverages	Natural juices	Citrus/acidic fruit juices	Coffee, black tea, fizzy/cola drinks
Other foods	-	Industrialized seasonings, spices and condiments (Ketchup, mayonnaise, mustard)	Mustard grain

8.3. Herbs and Probiotics for PUD Management

The potential of plants as source of new drugs still offers a large field for scientific research. Even if is observed a large number of known plants, a small percentage has already been phytochemically investigated and only a fraction of them has already been assessed to determine its pharmacological potential.

Exhibit 10. Herbs for PUD Management	
Plant name/family	Description
<i>Acacia arabica</i> (Mimosaceae)	Locally known as babul tree. Aqueous extract of <i>A. arabica</i> gum showed protection against meloxicam-induced intestinal damage and attenuated intestinal enzyme activity. Chemical constituents reported in this plant are gum containing arabic acid combined with calcium, magnesium, and potassium and also small quantity of malic acid, sugar, moisture 14%, and ash 3-4%. As gargle it is useful as wash in haemorrhagic ulcer and wounds [178].
<i>Psidium guajava</i> L., popularly known as guava (Myrtaceae)	The leaves have shown the ability to protect the stomach against ulceration by inhibiting gastric lesions, reducing gastric secretory volume, and acid secretion, and raising the gastric pH. This anti-ulcer activity, resulting from the protection of the mucosa, was related to the flavonoids in the leaves [179]
<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (Rutaceae), Bael Fruit	Ulcers are induced by aspirin plus pylorus ligated gastric ulceration in rats and aqueous extract of leaves is to be administered orally for 21 days, daily dose of 1 gm/kg. The result indicated a significant reduction in the ulcer lesion count compared to control [180]
<i>Allium sativum</i> (Liliaceae) garlic	Chemical constituents in this plant are an acrid volatile oil which is the active principle, starch, mucilage, albumen, and sugar. Seeds yield aromatic oil. The juice, more particularly its oil constituents, is rich in organically bound sulphur, iodine, and salicylic acid combinations, apart from important nutrient and complementary substances containing vitamins [178]. Garlic extract has been also studied to show suppressive effect of <i>Helicobacter pylori</i> -induced gastric inflammation in vivo and reduction of gastric cancer incidence in a clinical trial [181]. AGE corrected the histopathological abnormalities in gastric tissue and proved (investigated in an experimental model of indomethacin-induced gastric ulcer) a promising gastroprotective role in gastric ulcer [182].

Azadirachta indica(Meliaceae) Neem	Administration of lyophilized powder of the extract for 10 days at the dose of 30 mg twice daily showed significant decrease (77%) of gastric acid secretion. The bark extract at the dose of 30–60 mg twice daily for 10 weeks almost completely healed the duodenal ulcers and one case of esophageal ulcer and one case of gastric ulcer healed completely when administrated at the dose of 30 mg twice daily for 6 weeks [184]
<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> L. (Fabaceae)	Chemical constituents reported in this plant are quercetin, rutin, apigenin, and apigenin 7-0-glucoside. Bark contains tannin (tannic acid), glucose, and a brownish gum. The <i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> aqueous extract (BPAE) was prepared in the doses of 100, 500 and 1,000 mg/kg. Antiulcer activity of BPAE was evaluated by absolute ethanol- and indomethacin-induced gastric ulcer, and pyloric ligation models. Acute toxicity was also carried out. The BPAE exhibits antiulcer activity, which could be due to the presence of saponins or sugar-free polyphenols, and, thus, confirmed the traditional uses of <i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> in the treatment of ulcers [185]
<i>T. indica</i> (Caesalpinioideae) Tamarind	The methanolic extract of the seed coat of this plant (100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg) has been evaluated for determining their antiulcer potential on ibuprofen, alcohol and pyloric ligation-induced gastric lesions using albino Wistar rats [63]. The results of this study showed that the methanolic extract reduced total gastric juice volume and free and total gastric secretion acidity in pylorus ligation-induced ulcer model, while reduced ulcer index (comparable with ranitidine, 50 mg/kg, as control) [186]
Flavonoids	Also known as bioflavonoids, some research suggested that these molecules may be beneficial in stomach ulcers, naturally present in many fruits and vegetables such as apple, soybeans, berries, and broccoli. As a disorder of the GI tract, pathological conditions in peptic ulcer could be alleviated by nutritional factors. Dietary consumption of a significant amount of “natural” protective supplements in early life leads to prevention or delayed peptic ulcer [187]
Deglycyrrhizinated licorice	It is beneficial in <i>H. pylori</i> -associated ulcer. In modern medicine, licorice extract has been used for pepticulcer and as an alternative to bismuth that has a protective role against acid and pepsin secretions by covering the site of lesion and promoting the mucous secretion [188].
Honey	Natural honey is composed of around 82% carbohydrates, water, phytochemicals, proteins, minerals, and antioxidants. It is also beneficial in <i>H. pylori</i> -associated ulcer because honey is a powerful antibacterial agent. In gastric curative effects of manuka honey in rat model with acetic acid-induced chronic gastric ulcer, manuka honey provided significant gastroprotective effects in acute gastric ulcer animal model [189]

It has been shown that lactobacilli are particularly useful in promoting gastric ulcer healing in rats, when administered as an individual probiotic strain, such as *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG, *Lactobacillus gasseri* OLL2716, or *Lactobacillus acidophilus* or as a probiotic mixture, VSL#3. *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG increases the cellular proliferation to apoptosis ratio and therefore promotes regeneration of epithelial cells, particularly at the ulcer margins. In clinical studies, a probiotic mixture was demonstrated to be better than a single strain for improving the characteristics of indigenous microflora[191].

Exhibit 11. Summary of studies on the therapeutic effects of probiotics in Gastric Ulcer [191]			
Probiotic strain(s)	Modeling method	Lesions	Effects of probiotics
<i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.	Acetic acid	Gastric ulcer	Enhance healing of a pre-existing gastric ulcer
<i>Lactobacillus rhamnosus</i> GG	Acetic acid	Gastric ulcer	Inhibit cell apoptosis to proliferation ratio, and induce angiogenesis
<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i> OLL 2716	Acetic acid	Gastric ulcer	Accelerate healing by enhancing generation of gastric mucosal prostaglandin E2
<i>Lactobacillus acilidophilus</i> encapsulated in ginger extract	Stress	Gastric ulcer	Improve healing by restoring all biochemical, physiological and histological changes
<i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> and alginate floating beads	Stress	Gastric ulcer	Improve healing by restoring all biochemical, physiological and histological changes
Probiotic mixture (VSL#3) (8 probiotic strains)	Acetic acid	Gastric ulcer	Enhance healing by promoting angiogenesis via upregulation of vascular endothelial growth factor
<i>Saccharomyces boulardii</i>	Ibuprofen	Gastric ulcer	Potential treatment or prevention
Polysaccharides fractions (PSFs) of <i>Bifidobacterium breve</i> and <i>bifidum</i>	Acetic acid and ethanol	Gastric erosion and ulcer	Repair and protect gastric mucosa by increasing expression of epidermal and fibroblast growth factors and 6-ketoprostaglandin F1
Probiotic mixture (2 bacterial strains) and composite probiotic (3 bacterial strains)	Stress	Gastric erosion and ulcer	Reduce lesions and intensity of bleeding through the restoration of pro- and antioxidant balance
Probiotic mixture (14 bacterial strains)	Stress	Gastric mucosal lesions	Enhance recovery of stress hormones, downregulate pro-inflammatory cytokines and upregulate anti-inflammatory cytokines

Promising results for studies exploring both prophylactic and therapeutic effects (Exhibit 11) of probiotics have been obtained. The studies concerning the roles of probiotics in gastric ulcer healing reported in the literature were mainly conducted in rats. These studies were based on the use of either individual probiotic strains, such as *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG, *Lactobacillus gasseri* OLL2716, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917, *Bifidobacterium animalis* VKL/VKB, *Bifidobacterium bifidum/brevis* and *Saccharomyces boulardii*, or a mixture of probiotic strains, such as VSL#3. A number of studies have reported that probiotics not only inhibit the development of acute gastric mucosal lesions, but also accelerate the process of healing of induced gastric ulcers [191].

Figure 7. Mechanisms of action of probiotics.

Probiotics are engaged to adherence to host epithelial tissue, acid resistance and bile tolerance, elimination of pathogens or reduction in pathogenic adherence production of acids, hydrogen peroxide and bacteriocins antagonistic to pathogen growth, safety, non-pathogenic and non-carcinogenic, and Improvement of intestinal microflora. Prebiotics of proven efficacy are able to modulate the gut microbiota by stimulating indigenous beneficial flora while inhibiting the growth of pathogenic bacteria therein. Preferred target organisms for prebiotics are specific, belonging to the *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* genera. The most efficient prebiotics may also reduce or suppress numbers and activities of organisms seen as pathogenic (Bandyopadhyay B, Mandal NC. Probiotics, Prebiotics and Symbiotic - In Health Improvement by Modulating Gut Microbiota: The Concept Revisited. *Int. J.Curr. Microbiol. App. Sci* (2014) 3(3): 410-420)

Probiotics can also protect the integrity of the gastric mucosal barrier by upregulating prostaglandin, mucous secretion, tight junction protein expression and cell proliferation, and by inhibiting apoptosis (43,48,130–132). In rats, the administration of *Bifidobacterium bifidum* BF-1 or *Bifidobacterium animalis* VKL and VKB has been found to protect the gastric mucosa through either preventing the mucous barrier from degradation or increasing gastric mucous production. The probiotic mixture VSL#3 protects the epithelial barrier and upregulates the expression of tight junction proteins (occludin and zonula occludens-1) in vivo and in vitro via the activation of p38 or mitogen-activated protein (MAP) kinase and extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK) signaling pathways. Mennigen et al demonstrated that probiotics can strengthen the gastric mucosal barrier by inhibiting the redistribution and expression of tight junction proteins and blocking apoptosis (135). The probiotic strains *Lactobacillus gasseri* OLL2716, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG and *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917 are able to protect the altered gastric mucosal barrier (43,48,114). In humans, Gotteland et al found that pretreatment with *Lactobacillus* GG protected against indomethacin-induced disruption of the gastric mucosal barrier [191].

Exhibit 11. Selection criteria of probiotic strains [190]

Criterion	Required Properties
Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human or animal origin. • Isolated from the gastrointestinal tract of healthy individuals. • History of safe use. • Precise diagnostic identification (phenotype and genotype traits). • Absence of data regarding an association with infective disease. • Absence of the ability to cleave bile acid salts. • No adverse effects. • Absence of genes responsible for antibiotic resistance localized in non-stable elements.
Functionality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competitiveness with respect to the microbiota inhabiting the intestinal ecosystem. • Ability to survive and maintain the metabolic activity, and to grow in the target site. • Resistance to bile salts and enzymes. • Resistance to low pH in the stomach. • Competitiveness with respect to microbial species inhabiting the intestinal ecosystem (including closely related species). • Antagonistic activity towards pathogens (e.g., <i>H. pylori</i>, <i>Salmonella</i> sp., <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>, <i>Clostridium difficile</i>). • Resistance to bacteriocins and acids produced by the endogenic intestinal microbiota. • Adherence and ability to colonise some particular sites within the host organism, and an appropriate survival rate in the gastrointestinal system.
Technological usability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy production of high biomass amounts and high productivity of cultures. • Viability and stability of the desired properties of probiotic bacteria during the fixing process (freezing, freeze-drying), preparation, and distribution of probiotic products. • High storage survival rate in finished products (in aerobic and micro-aerophilic conditions). • Guarantee of desired sensory properties of finished products (in the case of the food industry). • Genetic stability. • Resistance to bacteriophages.

The mode of action of probiotics is not completely understood but they may act as surrogate normal microflora following antibiotic therapy until recovery is achieved. However, probiotic combinations appeared to induce only minor changes in the microbiota. For instance, the mechanisms of action of *S. boulardii* include luminal action (anti-toxic effect, antimicrobial activity), trophic action (enzymatic activity, increased IgA) and mucosal-anti-inflammatory signaling effects (decreased synthesis of inflammatory cytokines). Short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) and bacteriocin proteins have been implicated in the inhibition of *H. pylori* by lactic acid bacteria. SCFAs such as formic, acetic, propionic, butyric and lactic acids are produced as a result of the metabolism of carbohydrates by probiotics and play an important role in decreasing the pH in vitro. Their antimicrobial activity could be due to the inhibition of urease activity by high lactic acid producers, such as *Lactobacillus salivarius* and *Lactobacillus casei* Shirota. *Lactobacillus salivarius* significantly decreased IL-8 production [IL-8 is induced after injection of virulence factor CagA into epithelial cells] upon exposure to *H. pylori* and led to CagA accumulation in *H. pylori* cells, presumably as a result of loss of functionality of the Cag secretion system. Alterations in gastrointestinal permeability are an initial step in the development of lesions such as ulcers. Probiotics may stabilize the intestinal barrier by stimulating the expression of gastric mucins, decreasing bacterial overgrowth and stimulating local immune responses and the release of antioxidant substances [192].

Conclusion

This review is conducted and correlate the published literature on the effectiveness of herbs and probiotics, for the treatment of FAPDs. Despite its common use, research on the efficacy, safety, and optimal dosage remains limited. Many responsible members of the dietary supplements industry have taken significant steps to regain consumer trust by improving transparency along the supply chain, enhancing traceability of raw botanical materials, and bringing attention to ingredients with potential adulteration concerns, among other efforts. Lifestyle and food habit also found important factor to improve GI related disorders to much extent. Several randomized controlled trials have now shown that microbial modification by probiotics may improve gastrointestinal symptoms and multiorgan inflammation in rheumatoid arthritis, ulcerative colitis, and multiple sclerosis. In the USA, microorganisms used for consumption purposes should have the GRAS status, regulated by the FDA. In Europe, EFSA introduced the term of QPS. The QPS concept involves some additional criteria of the safety assessment of bacterial supplements, including the history of safe usage and absence of the risk of acquired resistance to antibiotics. Future work will need to carefully assess safety issues, selection of optimal strains and combinations, and attempts to prolong the duration of colonization of beneficial microbes. This doesn't mean conventional therapies don't work, it just means that experts haven't studied them enough to know if they do. The most important thing is safe healing and better life. To ensure this, researchers needs to work more on both conventional and complimentary drugs.

Abbreviations: The American College of Gastroenterology (ACG); Gastroesophageal Reflux Disease (GERD); Proton Pump Inhibitors (PPIs); Recurrent Abdominal Pain (RAP); Functional gastrointestinal disorders (FGIDs); Postprandial Distress Syndrome (PDS); Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM); Functional Dyspepsia (FD); Chronic Constipation (CC); Quality Of Life (QoL); European Society for Paediatric Gastroenterology Hepatology and Nutrition (ESPGHAN); North American Society for Pediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition (NASPGHAN); Congenital Sucrase-Isomaltase Deficiency (CSID); FODMAPs (Fermentable Oligosaccharides, Disaccharides, Monosaccharides and Polyols); SIBO (Small Intestinal Bacterial Overgrowth); NCGS (Nonceliac Gluten Sensitivity); ATIs (α -Amylase/Trypsin Inhibitors); Ni ACM (Nickel Allergic Contact Mucositis); Health-Related quality of life (HRQoL); Healthcare Resource Utilization (HRU); 5-Hydroxytryptamine-3 Receptor (5-HT₃); Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO); Department of Health (DOH); Artichoke Leaf Extract (ALE); Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD); Parkinson's Disease (PD); Crohn's Disease (CD); Ulcerative Colitis (UC); Dietary Supplement (DS); Extraintestinal Manifestations (EIMs); Crohn's Disease Activity Index (CDAI); Simple Endoscopic Score for Crohn's Disease (SES-CD); Peptic Ulcer Disease (PUD); Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD); Bauhinia Purpurea Aqueous Extract (BPAAE); Herbal Dietary Supplements (HDS); Generally Regarded As Safe (GRAS); Qualified Presumption of Safety (QPS); European Food Safety Authority (EFSA); Mitogen-Activated Protein (MAP); Extracellular Signal-Regulated Kinase (ERK); Short-Chain Fatty Acids (SCFAs); Cytotoxin-associated gene A (CagA)

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